

The Impact of Censorship Laws on Artistic Freedom: A Study of the ‘Chinthamani’ Play in Telugu Theatre

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Abstract:

Chinthamani performances in Telugu theatre caused debate and government intervention due to modern adaptations that added obscene scenes, particularly those that depicted Subbi Shetty, a member of Arya Vaishya community, in an offensive manner. As the play was banned by the state government, many people of Telugu speaking region expressed their disappointment. This research investigates the responses of Telugu theatre community to the ban on Chinthamani, and the research focuses on conflict between social standards and artistic freedom. This study draws upon the original script, the play’s historical significance, archival extracts, and social media responses in order to conduct a comprehensive analysis. Research was conducted through a mix of qualitative analysis of the themes and historical significance of the play, as well as quantitative surveys of the theatre community. Study findings emphasize social media’s role in mobilizing protests against the ban, the loss of theatre work due to the ban, and efforts to revoke the ban. Furthermore, the study emphasizes the importance of dialogue between theatre communities and government authorities in preserving cultural heritage and encouraging social commentary and artistic innovation.

Keywords: Chinthamani, Telegu Theatre, Ban, Societal standards, Artistic freedoms

1. Introduction:

In the history of Telugu theatre, “Chinthamani” is considered a groundbreaking piece that combines creative originality with a critical

examination of society. Authored by Kallakuri Narayana Rao and initially released in 1921, this play quickly resonated with the Telugu spectators due to its powerful depiction of social issues, notably the problem of prostitution. Its storytelling skills and literary excellence elevated it to a prominent position in Andhra Pradesh's theatrical realm, garnering lasting praise (Pothugunta 14).

Since its inception, “Chinthamani” has served as a reflective mirror of society, confronting audiences with the complexities of human morality and the consequences of vice. The play delves into a wide range of topics, from ethical quandaries to spiritual evolution, exploring the nuanced interplay between temptation, redemption, and societal norms. This rich narrative has not only engaged audiences but also established the play as a powerful tool for societal change and cultural self-reflection.

However, recent adaptations of “Chinthamani” have sparked renewed controversy due to deviations from the original intent and the inclusion of objectionable content, prompting the government to intervene. These adaptations, characterized by the introduction of vulgar language and insensitive portrayals, especially of the character Subbi Shetty, have sparked public outcry and legal scrutiny (S.V. 336; Kotte 33).

The play's journey must be understood within the broader context of censorship in Indian theatre history. Censorship has been an enduring issue in Indian theatre, reflecting the conflicts between artistic freedom, societal norms, and political tensions. First formal censorship law was introduced in India under British rule with the passage of the “Dramatic Performances Act of 1876” (Bhatia 6). Even after independence, colonial censorship frameworks were not abolished, but rather maintained and expanded (Ibid 89). Afterwards, the Cinematograph Act of 1952 was enacted to further restrict artistic expression (Maheswari 68). In independent India, censorship laws have frequently been utilized to govern speech and suppress political opposition. The actions are taken in response to a complaint of offense. The practice of censorship has had a significant impact on the advancement and artistic representation of Indian theatre. These impacts include the rise of self-censorship among artists and organizations, the stifling of political theatre and progressive movements, and the need for artistic adaptation to navigate restrictions.

The threat of violence and financial loss led many artists and organizations to self-censor, cancelling performances and exhibitions to avoid conflict (Maheshwari 333–339). Vijay Tendulkar's plays *Ghashiram Kotwal* and *Sakharam Binder* are examples of this phenomenon. Both the plays were attacked by Shiv Sena, an incident that went through the judicial process. The play, *Ghashiram Kotwal* was banned after 19 shows in 1970. Following protests, the ban was lifted in 1974. Similarly, *Sakharam Binder* was banned in 1974 on charges of obscenity under Section 292 of the IPC (Ibid 79). The main objection was its challenge to the sacred institution of marriage in the Maharashtrian Brahmin value system. This ban was also later revoked after the production team endured turbulent times. The incidents of extrajudicial censorship likely contributed to a chilling effect on artistic expression. As a result, some theatre practitioners were probably influenced to self-censor and avoid sensitive themes. The self-imposed restriction may have been a reflection of fear and uncertainty within the theatre community. As a result, some of the theatrical content may have become more homogenous as practitioners limited their topics of choice.

A further example of censorship's impact on artistic freedom is found in the practice of political theatre. The Indian People's Theatre Association (IPTA), a progressive movement that blended artistic expression with social activism through performing arts, faced government repression despite its cultural significance. In 1950, censorship practices and entertainment taxes by Congress contributed to the decline of IPTA (Ibid 104). The government's financial restrictions limited IPTA and similar groups to staging performances on sensitive political topics.

Activist and prominent street theatre personality Safdar Hashmi was murdered because he was perceived as a threat to the political power. In his performances, he critiqued the government and capitalist structures. His murder represents an attempt to silence an artist's critical and political voice. After Hashmi's death, the government's tardy response demonstrated bureaucratic inertia and a failure to address the underlying causes of violence and opposition (Ibid 111-112). The lack of timely action suppressed artistic expression. In this case, political power

influenced both the police and the judiciary to protect the murderers and delay justice. Here, political power illustrates how censorship is indirectly imposed through violence and institutional failures.

In reaction to Hashmi's death, intellectuals and artists protested outside the residence of Home Minister Buta Singh; they performed street plays at various places and opposed government-sponsored cultural events; they designated Hashmi's birthday as National Street Theatre Day; they held numerous art auctions to support cultural activities and events in honor of Safdar Hashmi; the Safdar Hashmi Memorial Trust (Sahmat) was founded in February 1989; and Sahmat initiated the 'Artists Alert' campaign (Ibid 108-115). These people's unified actions reject violent repression and endorse freedom of expression.

The reasons for banning Chinthamani performances share many similarities with Vijay Tendulkar's Sakharam Binder. The performances of both plays were banned due to their perceived obscenity and offensive representations of communities. However, Chinthamani's performances do not reflect the core values of Sakharam Binder, since the adaptations of Chinthamani were primarily centered on entertainment and attracting large audiences. The Telugu theatre community's mobilization in response to Chinthamani's ban resembles another incident in Indian theatre. The incident shares a common characteristic of uniting theatre personalities for a common cause. The common characteristic is observed between the response to Chinthamani's ban and the reaction to Hashmi's death. Both instances demonstrated theatre artists' unified actions.

In light of censorship, this study explores the reactions of theatre community to the restrictions placed on "Chinthamani," examining the conflicts between societal demands and artistic expression. The aim is to explore the intersections of censorship, politics, and artistic freedom in Telugu theatre by analyzing the historical context, cultural impact, and current debates related to the play's performance. This research analyses the consequences of censorship on artistic freedom in Telugu theatre and studies the theatre community's reactions to imposed bans. It identifies the contribution of social media in shaping a unified response to the ban. Using this comprehensive approach, the research intends to contribute

to broader discussions about balancing artistic integrity with societal norms in contemporary Telugu theatre. As it examines the case of “Chinthamani,” this study reveals artists’ challenges and strategies in navigating censorship while preserving cultural heritage.

2. Literature Review:

For this research paper, we have depended on script of the play, and the books and journals who reflected on the play since 1930. For this we have selected few books, and they are “Rayalaseemalo Ranga Sthalam Okatava Bhagam”, “Padyanataka Parijatham”, “Marapurani Manishi”, and “Godavari Seema Janapada Kalalu Kreedalu Vedukalu”. Other than this, to understand the present view on the play, we have referred newspaper clips, and social media responses. The existing literature review reports the themes of the play: social standards, spiritual values, and ethical consideration of prostitution.

It emphasized spiritual transformation of Bilwamangaludu from the person who was addicted to prostitution, and transformation of Chinthamani from courtesan to a nun. The literature review identified the popularity of Chinthamani from 1920 with its poetic richness. It revealed that Subbi Shetty character was already misinterpreted before year 2000, it also emphasized issues around respectful representation. This lead for major debates, and to protest from Arya Vaishya community and female spectators. The literature review also found that the ban on ‘Chinthamani’ has relevance within the broader history of censorship in Indian theatre.

The present research probably demonstrates lack of analysis of the spectators’ engagement from the first performance to present scenario, and societal impact of the play. It also presents limited comparison of various performances and its reception. In case of theoretical frameworks, the research adapted moral and socio-cultural analysis, ethical criticism and performance theory. These theories assist to identify the themes in the play, analysis of the characters, performance context, cultural context, and influence on spectators. Within this theoretical frame, the research identifies how the play performance of Chinthamani addresses ethical dilemmas, echoes social values, and influences the spectator in present scenario.

3. Methodology:

This research paper explores the responses of theatre practitioners to the ban of the play “Chinthamani,” employing a mixed methods approach. Initially, qualitative methods were utilized to delve into the themes, characters, and historical context of the play. Subsequently, a quantitative survey was used to gather 300 responses from theatre practitioners and cultural activists. These responses were collected through closed and open-ended questions. We also collected responses through social media platforms such as WhatsApp groups dedicated to Telugu theatre practitioners, Facebook, and YouTube videos. The mixed methods approach facilitated a comprehensive exploration of the ban’s impact on artistic freedom.

For the survey, Google Forms and telephonic interviews were employed; Theatre practitioners were randomly selected across different age groups ranging from 25 to 80 and professions within the Telugu theatre community—including playwrights, directors, musicians, makeup artists, actors, stage technicians, lighting technicians, journalists, professors, and critics. Semi-structured questions guided both the telephonic interviews and Google Forms, focusing on perceptions, experiences, and suggestions related to the ban. Analysis encompassed WhatsApp group messages and Facebook comments regarding the play’s ban, spanning from January 18, 2022, to May 30, 2024.

Quantitative data analysis involved descriptive statistics for closed-ended questions and coding for open-ended responses, aiding in the categorization of themes. To decode the qualitative data, the researchers depended on long sessions, poring over transcripts and digital responses. They used colorful sticky notes and sprawling mind maps to visualize emerging themes. For closed-ended questions, researchers utilized Google Forms’ “Summary of responses” feature, which automatically generates visual charts to provide a quick overview of the collected data. This approach provided insights into artistic freedom and the reflections of theatre practitioners regarding the ban.

However, the survey method via Google Forms yielded an insufficient number of responses, reflecting challenges in engaging current

practitioners of “Chinthamani.” Similarly, the telephonic interviews did not yield a substantial number of participants associated with recent performances of the play.

The strengths of the research methodology are very detailed textual analysis, evolution of historical context of the play, and the collecting the responses of the present generation. The weakness of the research methodology is the limited scope of performance analysis, and a smaller number of people who responded for the survey. Remarkably, theatre practitioners under 40 years old had a lower participation rate in the survey. This lack of response is probably due to their unfamiliarity with the play, and many of them from this age group neither watched the play performance nor read the play script.

4. Results:

The research investigates responses of theatre practitioners and cultural activists to the ban imposed on the play “Chinthamani”. This investigation focused on shared points among artistic freedom, social standards and political motivation. Firstly, this study found the historical significance of the play in Telugu speaking region. Then, it observes how theatre practitioners and cultural activists expressed discontent and concern over the ban. This research identified the significant role of social media in influencing theatre practitioners and cultural activists to protest the ban. Furthermore, the study explored the possibility of rifts within the theatre community as a result of political involvement in the protests. It identified the complex responses for an inquiry based on economic challenges and the loss of theatre work caused by the ban on theatre professionals who have been performing the play since the late 1980s. Immediately following the ban announcement, the theatre community discussed possible approaches to revoking it. These discussions suggested several initiatives to revoke the ban. These initiatives included removing unpleasant scenes, notifying theatre professionals who misinterpreted the play, requesting the formation of government review panels, organizing formal protests, and taking legal action.

Thus, the study examines in detail the impact of the ban on “Chinthamani.” It demonstrates a conflict between the expression of

theatre personalities and social norms. Majority of the responses expressed concern about rescinding the ban and preserving the original script's value. The results suggests that theatre community avoid overly explicit content in order to reach a larger audience. The majority of respondents favored careful self-regulation in play interpretations. The study recommends a fair censorship approach that ensures the preservation of artistic freedom while respecting community standards.

5. Discussion:

The study reflects on the cultural significance of Chinthamani through an analysis of its characters, themes, and historical background. This analysis examines the complexities of character representation and the underlying themes in the original text, as well as recent interpretations. This discussion explores how the theatre community unites during demonstrations, how social media offers support, and the impact of bans on public perceptions. The analysis explores the correlation between the responses of theatre artists, societal norms, and political influences within the scope of the ban.

5.1. Character's Overview:

In the play, there are eleven characters, each portraying distinct social roles and ethical positions.

Bilwamangaludu is the protagonist of the play. His introduction to Chinthamani, a courtesan, causes his personality to undergo a significant change. This transformation illustrates the progression from personal choices to spiritual enlightenment. He is initially depicted as a pleasure-seeking individual. Later on, he gets caught up in deep personal conflicts, ultimately achieving redemption through these challenging experiences.

Chinthamani also transforms in the story. She embodies core human values and transformation capacity, even in seemingly unchangeable circumstances. She always raises ethical concerns about her profession. She rebels against her mother, and at the end of the play, she becomes a nun. Her transformation from courtesan to nun illustrates the conflict between societal expectations and personal decisions. Chinthamani cunningly and decisively manipulates others as per her mother's request.

Overall, Chinthamani is a complex individual who deals with her own moral struggles.

Vasudevamurthy, the father of Bilwamangaludu, demonstrated parental control and adherence to traditional beliefs. Vasudevamurthy contradicts with his son's rebellious decisions. Regularly, he warns his son concerning the risks associated with infatuation with Chinthamani. Vasudevamurthy's departure greatly shapes the transformation of Bilwamangaludu. Thus, Vasudevamurthy navigates family relationships, exhibits a deep sense of responsibility and shapes the narrative.

Damodarudu provides consistent guidance and steadfast support to his close friend Bilwamangaludu. Damodarudu is depicted with a strong sense of integrity, and he demonstrates a polished sense of humour. As a scholarly person, he embodies traditional values.

Subbi Shetty, a merchant (a member of Arya Vaishya), is portrayed as a naive and playful individual in the story. His speech and actions reveal his lack of knowledge about the world. He becomes a victim of Srihari's schemes, Chinthamani's mother. Subbi Shetty loses considerable wealth due to his promiscuity, initially to Ranganayaki and then to Chinthamani. His innocent and humorous actions provide comic relief throughout the play.

Bhavani Shankarudu is a wealthy individual who seeks comedic sexual encounters. He exemplifies the harmful impacts of unregulated desires. He leaves his attractive wife, disconnects from his family, and loses all of his belongings in order to be with Chinthamani. Following his surrender to her charm, he encounters various difficulties arising from this romantic relationship. Bhavani Shankar admits to a decline in his sanity and dignity through self-examination. He expresses sincere regret for his actions. He displays self-pity, personal weakness, and a heartfelt self-examination in his struggle for Chinthamani.

Somagiri Yogindrudu, an intellectual, preaches and guides others, and he demonstrates the highest humanitarian values. During Bhavani Shankar's life of infatuation and ego, Somagiri Yogindrudu guides him towards spiritual enlightenment. Somagiri Yogindrudu disapproves of Chinthamani's behaviour, but guides her with humanitarian values.

Lord Krishna influences the characters' destinies and ethical dilemmas.

Radha, the wife of Bilwamangaludu, represents faithfulness and dedication. She displays open-mindedness despite being a traditional homemaker. Radha possesses beauty, and she radiates love, trust, and self-respect. Radha symbolizes both passion and fulfilment in her life by relentlessly fighting to win back her husband from Chinthamani. Radha remains optimistic despite the challenges and pain she faces. Her tragic death and steadfast devotion profoundly influenced Bilwamangaludu's journey.

Srihari, the greedy mother of Chinthamani, controls Chinthamani's choices. She impresses others with her cleverness, often fooling them. Srihari's relentless pursuit of material gain influences Chinthamani's actions. Srihari's nature embodies the greed that guides Chinthamani into morally ambiguous dilemmas.

Chitra, a young and innocent girl, is Chinthamani's maid. Even though she is too young to be involved in prostitution, she undergoes maturation under Srihari's guidance in the Chinthamani household. She monitors Chinthamani's decisions and suggests alternatives when possible. She is admired by spectators for her innocence. As a result of their interactions, these eleven characters advance the plot and illuminate ethical, religious, and communal concerns.

5.2. Synopsis of Chinthamani:

Due to the influence of her mother, Chinthamani uses her charm to manipulate men. By luring Bhavani Shankarudu and Subbi Shetty, she steals their wealth. Bhavani Shankarudu's infatuation with Chinthamani triggers a chain of events. Despite the consequences, he lavishly spends on Chinthamani.

Bilwamangaludu lives with his wife, Radha, in a peaceful and contented environment. He initially learns of Chinthamani's reputation, beauty, and virtue. Bilwamangaludu is captivated by Chinthamani's charm when they first meet, causing him to gradually neglect his familial responsibilities. At one point, he even disregards the death of his father in order to devote himself to Chinthamani. In the midst of a stormy night, Bilwamangaludu

is driven by his infatuation to meet Chinthamani. During that day, Radha, his wife, follows Bilwamangaludu out of a deep concern for his safety, love, and devotion, and to protect him from his destructive path. They arrive at a river that he must cross in order to reach the residence of Chinthamani. In order to get a boat, Radha leaves him on the riverbank. In the meantime, Bilwamangaludu jumps into the flooded river in order to cross it. Mistaking a body for a log, he uses it to cross. Tragically, it is Radha's body; she had fallen from a cliff while attempting to bring a boat. This incident profoundly affects Bilwamangaludu, leading to a spiritual metamorphosis. Seeking solace and guidance from Sage Somadeva, Bilwamangaludu eventually embraces an ascetic life as Yogi LeelaShuka Krishna and composes the Sanskrit text "Krishna Karnamritam".

Meanwhile, Chinthamani decides to renounce her previous life and embrace a new path as a nun, following a profound realization of the repercussions of her actions and finding inspiration in an encounter with Lord Krishna. The narrative delves into the intricate nature of human desires and the quest for atonement through an exploration of themes such as temptation, ethical choices, and spiritual growth.

5.3. Historical Significance:

Chinthamani has played a significant role in Telugu Padya Natakamu (verse-drama) with social theme. The play demonstrates poetic richness with music and songs. With the poetic richness, the play attracted millions of Telugu spectators' hearts. In Telugu theatre history, the play has been performed widely and it has been recognized as one of the popular plays in Telugu for last 100 years. Before the play published, the play was performed successfully more than hundreds of the times. The play had been performed 440 times by the time of the release of its fourth edition on the 10th of January, 1923 (Kallakuri 2). Within the short periods reaching these many numbers of performances suggests that the play was accepted and popularized by many Telugu speaking spectators. The play has been performing on the celebration of Hindu festivals, such as Dusehramavarathir and Shrirama-navami. As the play was so popular, it was also adapted into films in 1933 and 1956. In 1933, the film version of Chinthamani was adapted directed by Kallakuri Sadasiva Rao and produced

by Madan Theatres (Volga et al. 73). In the 1956, Ramakrishna Rao adapted the play into film and released (Rajadhyaksha and Willemen 345).

The theme of the play strongly suggests to educate people against prostitution, reflects societal injustices towards a woman, and presents the exploitation of young children (Kallakuri 2; Kotte 27). The theme was communicated with a lot of humor and wit. Especially, the character Subbi Shetty plays significant role in creating humor and wit, and the character has been delighted Telugu spectators, and it contributed a lot to the plays success. This character was created by the playwright after he was inspired by observing a merchant in Kakinada (Kotte 31). Along with the humor, the play also demonstrates devotional scenes, and these scenes deeply touched the Telugu spectators in early 1930s. One such example was recounted by Ramachandraiah Tirumala, describing a performance around 1932 in Vizianagaram. During this event, a spectator, deeply moved by the depiction of a devotional act in the final scene featuring Bilwamangaludu, rushed onstage to embrace the actor portraying Bilwamangaludu and offered items originally intended for his daughter's wedding (Tirumala 123). The scene at the end of the play also portrays a revolutionary theme: a woman who ultimately rebels against her own profession as a prostitute. This scene resonated with many Telugu spectators and significantly influenced community perceptions. As Tulasi Balakrishna reflects the play's moral narrative discouraged prostitution, and historical accounts suggest that the play led some individuals to refrain from associating with prostitution after witnessing its performances (27 Jan. 2022).

However, over time, the play was adapted by many people, and these adaptations were performed by many troupes. This lead competition among the troupes to attract spectators for their performances. Results of this, the troupes gradually included many obscene scenes to attract the large number of spectators. The inclusion of obscene scenes into the original script led to controversy and offense to women, children, and particularly community of Arya Vaishya (Pothugunta 32). Despite this negative impression, the poetry, verses, and sensible humor of the original play attracted a large number of spectators and created significant impression on Telugu people. It is evident that the characters in the play "Chinthamani" have depicted the lives of many people from the 1900s

to the present. This enduring relevance demonstrates the play's ability to attract diverse audiences over time.

The debate over the prohibition of the play highlights the essential requirement for continuous communication between artists, communities, and authorities. It emphasizes the significance of maintaining artistic authenticity. The controversy calls for a balanced approach to artistic expression and cultural respect. This serves as a reminder to artists that their work may have an impact on society. As a result, it offers an insightful lesson regarding the interaction between community rights and creative freedom.

5.4. Controversies and Community Reactions:

There are seemingly three primary reasons for banning "Chinthamani": obscenity, morality, and community representation. In the original script, Kallakuri Narayana Rao intended to highlight the immoral actions of prostitution and the exploitation of girls. His aim was to educate people on these issues and discourage such practices (Kotte 27). However, later adaptations of the play included obscene scenes and language not present in the original script (S.V. 336). These adapted scenes began to offend female attendees and children (Kotte 32). This shift in the performance script led to a clash with societal norms.

The obscenity reached its peak through the portrayal of the characters Subbi Shetty and Shrihari. The character of Subbi Shetty was depicted on stage wearing a white dress and with a black-painted face, which triggered protests from the Arya Vaishya community. They expressed their dissatisfaction with this representation, feeling it was derogatory and portrayed their community negatively (Kotte 33). Gradually, the depiction of the character became increasingly obscene, and as the obscenity grew, the protests from the Arya Vaishya community intensified, leading to petitions to the government.

Along with the appearance of the Subbi Shetty character, many interpretations and adaptations that varied from the original script have led to controversy. The playwright designed this character with the intention to entertain the audience with sensible comedy, including the action of

stumbling towards the brothel in a drunken state (Kotte 31). Despite the playwright's intention, various troupes misinterpreted and adapted the character with vulgar dialogues and gestures, contributing to the play's negative reception. It seems that the Arya Vaishya community itself encouraged the original version of the character Subbi Shetty in the 1960s. According to Rangareddy, the community sponsored the play with that kind of characterization, and many spectators from that community enjoyed the play at that time. Aravapalli Subbarao founded the Royal Theatre in 1936 and gained popularity with Chinthamani (Sastri and Chakravarty 131). It is argued that Subbarao, a member of the Arya Vaishya community and a prominent theatre organizer, misinterpreted the play Chinthamani in its early days (Yallapragada). However, the majority of the evidence suggests that many theatre practitioners and spectators, along with the Arya Vaishya community, did not accept the incorrect interpretation of Subbi Shetty. A dominant group of spectators viewed Subbi Shetty as a humorous character meant for entertainment in the original play. Reflecting on the original script, very few spectators found the character offensive and derogatory. However, a large number of theatre practitioners recognized the character's evolution from comic relief to obscene actions.

Several Arya Vaishya organizations submitted petitions to Dr. Rajat Bhargava, IAS, Andhra Pradesh's Special Chief Secretary, concerning matters related to Chinthamani. On January 6, 2021, Konnakalla Vidhyadhara Rao from the "Vijayawada Urban District Arya Vaishya Sanghamu" filed the first petition. Shortly after, on January 10, 2021, Puvvada Chandra Shekhar, the founder president of the "Arya Vaishya Officials and Professionals Association," Andhra Pradesh, also submitted a petition. Mukkala Dwarakanadh, President of the "Arya Vaishya Mahasabha," Andhra Pradesh, followed with a petition on January 19, 2021. Later in the year, on June 16, 2021, Miththili Sarada, President of the "Vijayawada Urban District Arya Vaishya Sanghamu-Mahila Vibhagam," submitted another petition. Devaki Venkateshwarlu, Honorable President of the "International Vaishya Federation" Vijayawada, contributed a petition on June 25, 2021. The final petition in this series was submitted by Boddu Srinivasa Rao, "Governor of Vasavi Club International," on August 30, 2021. Arya Vaishya community petitions

voiced collective concerns about “Chinthamani’s” themes and representations.

The petitions submitted to the government requesting to ban the play demonstrated various concerns. A dominant concern for most the organizations is the task of adapting characters with offensive language, particularly in the case of Subbi Shetty. This offensive text veers away from the original play text. According to the petitioners, the misrepresentation brings dishonour to the Arya Vaishya community. Furthermore, the petitioners strongly oppose any disrespectful representation of the community. They emphasize the play’s negative social effects. According to them, using vulgar language in “Chinthamani” for profit undermines the educational purpose of the play and misleads children.

They pointed out that the revised version included erotic film songs. This misrepresentation was deemed detrimental to the youth and societal values. Furthermore, this showed disrespect towards revered figures and deities, causing unrest within the community. The performances portrayed women in a negative light and used inappropriate language, contradicting the play’s initial goal of enlightening and uplifting society. Thus, the petitioners collectively urge the government to ban the play, arguing that it deviates from the original text and could harm social values. This plea for intervention reflects a broader concern about upholding cultural authenticity and safeguarding the community from misrepresentation and exploitation for financial gain.

The protest by the Arya Vaishya community triggered government intervention in the work of theatre practitioners. Alongside the community, many others expressed dissatisfaction with the play’s obscene language and misinterpretations. Initially, Dwarkanath, the leader of Arya Vyshya Mahasabha, met with Chief Minister Y. S. Jagan Mohan Reddy to explain the issue (Janyala). He also submitted a petition to ban the play. As many believe, the community concerns prompted immediate political attention here. The ban was put into effect several months following their initial meeting. Rajat Bhargava, Special Chief Secretary, issued G.O. No. 7, officially prohibiting the play’s staging (Rao). This state-issued decree marked a significant change in artistic expression regulation.

Many theatre practitioners were unaware of the government officials' report, and they reflected that following Dwarkanath's meeting, there had been ample time to guide those involved in the production of the play "Chinthamani." They believed that such guidance could have potentially prevented the ensuing conflict between the community and theatre practitioners. However, it appeared that this guidance was not provided, resulting in an inability to resolve their differences. Additionally, the government had the opportunity to organize a committee comprising senior theatre practitioners, which they seemingly failed to do. Several theatre practitioners indicated that such a committee could have facilitated a platform for constructive discussions and mutual understanding. This lack of communication and engagement between the government and the theatre community highlighted the necessity for improved approaches in managing cultural conflicts.

5.5. Unified Response of Theatre Professionals to the Ban:

Theatre practitioners, regardless of their roles, voiced discontent with the play's prohibition. This unified response demonstrated their deep appreciation for the play. They identified that the ban threatened other plays as well (Sivvala). Many of them were initially shocked by the ban, and they were left unprepared. Later, they took action to defend the value of the play. They requested government officials to rescind the ban, explaining the play's significance. The requests were conveyed through formal letters, petitions, and personal discussions with officials. The theatre community emphasized the play's historical significance, cultural significance, and role in addressing social issues. They protested to preserve the play's authenticity for future generations. This dedication illustrates their commitment to protecting not only the play, but also Telugu cultural heritage in general.

Several prominent playwrights recommending that misinterpretations be corrected rather than the play being banned. Shiva Prasad Valluri argued that the ban on the play was an extreme action that did not effectively address the underlying problem. Krishneswara Rao Yallapragada emphasized the play's intricate literary and societal significance was not fully understood by the government. The playwrights underlined the

need to prevent inaccurate interpretations to safeguard the play's value. The playwrights' suggestions indicate that upcoming performances should stay faithful to the play's original purpose and essence.

The actors displayed mixed responses to the ban. While opposing the misinterpretation of the original play, they also raised concerns about ethical considerations and livelihood of the members who were involved with Chinthamani. Many expressed that they lose their livelihood if the government do not revoke the ban on the play. Some of the actors expressed to voluntarily remove the obscene scenes to mitigate objections. This suggests their realization to preserve the original play script. This voluntary response emphasized theatre practitioners' approach to address community sensitivities while requesting to revoke the ban on the play. In this case, adaptability of theatre practitioners probably indicates their commitment to balancing artistic freedom and social values within their work.

Member of many theatre groups organized formal protest and petitioned against ban. These efforts demonstrate a strategic and collective responses. Some of the groups are Gummadi Jairaj Kalapitam, Royal Seema Kalavedika, All India Kala Rangam, Praja Natya Mandali; Telugu Dandu, Adarsha Grameena Samskrutika Seva Samstha; Andhra Pradesh Kalakarula Sankshema Sangham, Andhra Pradesh Rashtra Sanskruthika Mariyu Nataka Prishath and Aravinda Arts. The groups are from different regions and communities, and they highlighted the unified stance of the theatre community in protecting freedom of theatre artists.

One of the prominent groups that organized a protest was Gummadi Jairaj Kalapitam. On January 23, 2022, the president, Sri Gummadi Jeevan Kumar, and the secretary, Sri Aguru Trinath Naidu, held a gathering at Kautha Purnananda Kala Vedika, Gandhi Nagar, Vijayawada. In this meeting, theatre practitioners, playwrights, poets and cultural activist gathered and voiced their disagreement with the ban of the play. They reflected on the significance of the play, and they concluded meeting to urge the government to revoke the ban. In the same way, under the leadership of M. R. Ganta, Rayala Seema Kalavedika submitted a petition to the chairman of Sangeet Natak Akademi, Sri Chamaluru Haritha. In the petition, they mentioned to revoke the ban. All India

Kalaragam also made their voice heard by submitting a petition to the village secretariat office in Pothavaram, Prakasam district. In their petition, the members highlighted the injustice of the ban, emphasizing the adverse effects on theatre practitioners and calling for its immediate revocation.

On the 73rd Republic Day, January 26, 2022, Praja Natya Mandali and other theatre professionals gathered at Kaleswara Rao Market in Vijayawada to express their solidarity and commitment to supporting artistic expression (G.V.). This gathering on a national holiday illustrates the symbolic significance of the protest. Here, theatre practitioners presented a petition to the statue suggests two significant protest methods. First, it indicates that theatre practitioners cleverly critiqued the government's lack of responsiveness by comparing it to the statue's immobility. Second, selecting the statue reflects Gandhi's legacy of non-violent resistance, which aligns with the theatre community's peaceful protests. In this protest, theatre practitioners highlighted the financial hardship faced by families who depend on the play, *Chinthamani*. In her speech, Rathnashree, a senior actress, requested that the government revoke the ban and support the families of theatre employees who have been performing the play for many years. G.V. Ranga Reddy, Praja Natya Mandali's state president, echoed the willingness of theatre practitioners to stick with the original script.

On January 19, 2022, in Sri Potti Sriramulu Nellore, All India Kala Rangam and Nellore Jilla Kala Sanghalu jointly protested in front of the Collector's Office. Members of the group expressed their disappointment with the ban. They stated that the ban had a negative impact on their profession due to the fact that they had been entertaining the public and relying on "*Chinthamani*" to earn their living. In his remarks, Madugula Sudheer, Founding President of All India Kalaramangam and a traditional harmonist for theatre performances, stated that the play's ban led to him losing a great deal of theatre work. The demonstration suggests that the ban negatively affects the economy of many theatre practitioners and demonstrates the urgency of lifting the ban.

Paravastu Phanisayana Suri from Telugu Dandu organized a protest against the ban at the Telugu Thalli Statue near Maddilapalem Junction in

Visakhapatnam on January 23, 2022 (“Drama Artists Protest” 0:20-1:20). It is possible that this protest contributed to an increasing number of people opposing the ban since Visakhapatnam is one of the dominant centers for Telugu theatre. The aim of the protest was to unite theatre practitioners in expressing their collective disapproval of the ban. According to Apparao, a renowned actor from the popular TV show *Jabardast*, numerous theatre practitioners across various departments - including actors, costume designers, prop makers, makeup artists, and musicians - depend on Chinthamani performances for their livelihood (Ibid 1:21-2:09).

The Andhra Pradesh Kalakarula Sankshema Sangham (APKSS) from Tadepallegudem also made substantial efforts to resist the prohibition. The members of the group met deputy Chief minister Pamula Pushpa Srivani to submit a petition to revoke the ban. As mentioned, she responded positively, assuring that she would find a solution suitable for both the theatre community and the Arya Vaishya community. The positive response provided optimism to the members of APKSS and to other theatre practitioners.

On January 19, 2022, the Vijayanagaram-based Rangasthala Kalaakaarula Sankshema Sangham (RKSS) staged a protest against the ban near the local Collector’s office. Along with RKSS members, Bhisetti Babji, president of the Dr. P.V.G. Raju Kala Vedika, urged the government to revoke the ban (Rao). The protest emphasized widespread opposition originating from Vizianagaram.

In addition to others, Aravinda Arts, a theater group based in Tadepalli Gudem, opposes the ban. In a personal interview, Gangothri Sai, director of the group, discussed the importance of depicting the community respectfully. His view emphasizes the importance of a balanced approach between artistic expression rights and artists’ accountability when depicting a community in the arts.

Collective action across theatre groups demonstrates the power of organized protest in the arts sector. Theatre professionals demonstrate their commitment to preserving their artistic heritage and financial stability. An appeal for financial assistance and other alternatives in relation to the prohibition on Chinthamani performances emphasizes the relationship

between an economic perspective and creative expression. Theatre professionals' answers make it clear that they have a shared ethical duty to support a responsible rendition of "Chinthamani". The community's active participation in the discussion about censorship reflects a nuanced understanding of balancing artistic freedom with societal norms.

5.6. Impact of Digital Platforms: From Social Media to Public Protest

Throughout the Covid-19 pandemic, social media was instrumental in fostering widespread public discourse and the exchange of opinions. The virtual forum created during the pandemic was quickly adapted by the theatre community as a means of facilitating dialogue on a variety of topics. The State government of Andhra Pradesh imposed an 11 pm to 5 am curfew and other COVID-19 measures, effective from January 18, 2022 ("Covid-19 Threat"). The ongoing impact of COVID-19 in the state also forced many practitioners and cultural activists to rely on social media to discuss the play's ban. As of January 2022, India's most commonly used platforms are WhatsApp, YouTube, and Facebook (Basuroy). The data for this study also suggests that Telugu-speaking theatre practitioners also actively used these platforms to spread their views, seek support, and coordinate protests and petitions. Some of the examples for such communications include text messages; multimedia sharing; comments and replies; reactions and likes; and group chats.

These communications substantiated to encourage solidarity against the ban and highlight artistic freedom in the public domain. The social media interactions within the theatre community fasten to meet at physical space, to organize protests, to facilitate thorough conversations, and to approach legally. Furthermore, these physical gathering cultivated partnership among different cultural groups.

The survey data conducted for this study highlights the fear and strong disappointment of theatre practitioners and cultural activists regarding the ban of the play "Chinthamani." The survey revealed that theatre practitioners believe the ban significantly influences their choice of themes, topics, characterizations, and representations in their future work, viewing it as a violation of their creative liberties. Additionally, discussions on social media by theatre practitioners echoed the sentiment

that the ban was politically motivated. Some practitioners also feared that the ban could cause divisions within the theatre community: one between contemporary performers of “Chinthamani” and other theatre practitioners; and another based on affiliations with the ruling party and the opposition party.

This disappointment led to various suggestions that addressed the concerns raised by the ban. The data also indicates that theatre practitioners and cultural activists plan to integrate these suggestions to develop a clear approach to the issue and preserve the freedom of artistic expression. The suggestions provided by theatre practitioners and cultural activists include: cutting obscene parts; issuing serious warnings to performers engaging in obscene acts; establishing a committee to review the performance text of “Chinthamani”; altering the names of characters in the play; protesting and appealing to lift the ban; sticking to the original script; government regulation of performances; reflecting on the performance approach; petitioning the High Court; gathering letters from theatre practitioners and cultural activists; and questioning government censorship.

5.5.1. Cutting Obscene Parts:

Many practitioners suggested removing scenes that represent the character Subbi Shetty in an obscene manner, as well as deleting objectionable dialogues and scenes from the performance text. Ramachandar Rao Tadakamalla, a senior theatre practitioner, also proposed that the court could delete a few obscene scenes in the text if necessary and then lift the ban.

5.5.2. Warning Seriously the Performers Who Perform Obscene Parts:

Some theatre practitioners expressed that the government should have warned the troupes to remove the obscene parts in the play before imposing a ban. A warning could have been a more prudent approach than directly banning the play. Additionally, there was a sentiment that the ban should specifically target those troupes that misinterpreted the play.

5.5.3. Forming a Committee to Review the Performance Text of Chinthamani:

Kameswararao N.S. and D.S.N. Murthy recalls similar instances of bans in Maharashtra, where plays like Tamasha and Vijay Tendulkar's "Sakharam Binder" were initially banned but later reinstated after government officials reviewed them properly. Practitioners recommended that the government establish a committee made up of academics and senior theater professionals to examine and revise the performance text of Chinthamani. The government could base its decision to impose the ban on the committee's final recommendation. The practitioners believed there was bias in the government's decision to ban the play and that there was insufficient consideration of all relevant factors. This implies that rather than imposing complete bans based on the complaints of a single community, censorship should be approached with more nuance and knowledge.

5.5.4. Changing the Name of the Characters in the Play:

Some theatre practitioners believed that changing the name of the character Subbi Shetty to a non-caste-specific name could help avoid objections and potentially allow the play to be considered a social play by the government. They also suggested changing the title of the play and removing obscene scenes to gain acceptance.

In a recent telephone conversation with Srinivasarao Addanki (popularly known as Srinivasarao Alla Kunta), the play's organizer, he revealed that the play is now being staged under the new title "Bhaktha Chinthamani" instead of original title "Chinthamani." Additionally, he mentioned that the character Subbi Shetty has been renamed Subba Rao. A poster for the upcoming performance on July 16, 2024, at the Nagulu Meera Swami temple in Ramayapalli Gramam, Hanumanthunipadu Mandalam, Prakasham district was shared by Srinivasarao Addanki, featuring the characters' names and photos of the actors in their respective roles. In the poster, despite the name change from Subbi Shetty to Subba Rao, the costume and makeup for the character remain unchanged from the previous representation of Subbi Shetty. Srinivasa Rao noted that the play has continued to be performed after the ban and has not

been stopped by anyone. His perspective contrasts with that of other theatre practitioners who have raised concerns about losing work due to the ban.

These suggestions to modify the name of characters and title of the play possibly approved the play “Chinthamani” has adapted to overcome objections and continued to perform. The performance group changed the play’s title to avoid censorship and renamed Subbi Shetty to a common name to avoid caste-based objections. Along with these changes, they also probably removed obscene scenes from the performances. These changes possibly allowed various theatre groups to perform the play without authorities’ intervention. These re-adaptations probably preserve the original text’s essence.

5.5.5. Protesting and Appealing to Lift the Ban:

Theatre practitioners and cultural activists organized protests and appealed to the government to lift the ban. They gathered and demonstrated unity, emphasizing their freedom of expression and the importance of the play to their community. These protests were aimed at showing the collective disagreement with the ban and urging the government to reconsider its decision.

5.5.6. Adhering to the Original Script:

Theatre practitioners expressed their commitment to perform “Chinthamani” without adding any dialogues, songs, or dances that deviate from the original script.

5.5.7. Regulating the Performance by Government:

Theatre practitioners believed that the government should pass an order to ensure performances adhere to decency and cultural values.

5.5.8. Reflection on Performance Approach:

Senior theatre practitioners requested that performers need to reflect on how they present the play. Some practitioners acknowledged past mistakes and expressed the need to correct their interpretations of the play to avoid future issues.

5.5.9. Petitioning the High Court:

Ramachandar Rao Tadakamalla suggested that theatre practitioners write formal letters to the Chief Justice of the High Court of Andhra Pradesh, asking for these letters to be considered as public interest litigation to lift the ban. Additionally, few theatre practitioners discussed about submitting affidavits to the High Court, promising to perform only the original script without obscene scenes.

After the PIL is filed on the ban, the deliberation of the High Court brought significant issues associated with censorship, community sentiments and freedom of expression. The court questioned why the stage play is banned while the novel *Chinthamani* remain uncensored (“High Court Questions Government Ban”). This discrepancy raises a concerns that the regulation or censorship of stage plays is not regulated by a statutory authority in India, unlike films. According to Section 95 of the Criminal Procedure Code, films are typically regulated by the Central Board of Film Certification (CBFC). In one of the hearings, a division bench stressed the delicate balance between freedom of expression and the possibility of offending others (“Andhra Pradesh HC Refuses to Stay Ban”). The bench also revealed that that it is impossible to issue a stay order without reviewing the play’s content. Trinath, theatre artist, and Raghu Rama Krishna Raju, Member of Parliament, are the petitioners, and they were instructed to provide a copy of the play and its English translation to the court. Approximately after one year since the play was ban, in the hearing, court recommends that the government establish a committee of artists to address the concerns raised in order to avoid a blanket ban on staging the play due to obscenity (V.). The case remains pending, but the theatre practitioners are performing the play with changing the name of the play and name of the Subbi Shetty.

5.5.10. Collecting Letters from Theatre Practitioners and Cultural Activists:

Administrators of Prajanatya Mandali and other theatre groups planned to collect and submit letters to the director of the cultural department of Andhra Pradesh, requesting the lifting of the ban on “*Chinthamani*” (G.V.).

5.5.11. Questioning Government Censorship:

Theatre practitioners questioned why the government bans the play but allows the movie version to remain available on YouTube. They argue that if the play is banned, then the movie, based on the same script, should also be banned. They also expressed that censor boards should be consistent in their regulation across different mediums. Some theatre practitioners compared the play performance with the TV show “Jabardast,” questioning why “Jabardast” is not banned even though it ridicules many identities. A few theatre practitioners pointed out that various Telugu movies also represent different communities. They asked whether, in this case, the government would ban those movies as well. They reasoned that if anybody bans any play based on caste, religion, or other backgrounds, no one can perform any play in the world.

Some reflected that obscene content is available in folk theatre forms and questioned whether the government would ban those as well. They noted that if folk theatre forms are banned, there would be no entertainment medium for the poor. Others questioned government officials and politicians who used foul language in public meetings and media, pointing out that they are not held accountable in the same way as the play was banned. These questions from the theatre practitioners suggest they are challenging the government for ignoring similar or worse content in other mediums.

5.6. Political Motivations and Community Divisions: The Complex Dynamics of the Ban

However, discussions on social media and physical platforms have also led to community division and exposed political motivations. These discussions often escalated existing tensions within the community, and led to conflicting viewpoints. A potential example of such a discourse unfolded at the Telugu Desam Party (TDP) office in Tenali, where a press conference was conducted and later shared on various social media channels (“TDP office Tenali’s Video” 00:01-05:40). The video featured few theatre practitioners requesting government to revoke the ban, and allow to perform the play without Subbi Shetty. This video ignited debates as the press conference was organized in the TDP party

office. This video influenced many theatre practitioners to believe that the issue was politicalized. This incident emphasized tension between political interests and cultural values.

Bharadwaj Govindaraju argues that the play's ban, aimed at appeasing a specific community, escalated tensions and compromised the protection of artistic freedom. This interpretation suggests the government implemented the ban for political expediency. Bharadwaj's observation coincides with Satyaarayana Y.'s viewpoint, as he also pointed out that political motivation was a major factor influencing the government's decision to impose the ban. One may question this perspective in light of a 2014 news report highlighting the police's decision to suspend performance permits for the play due to public unrest. According to the newspaper, certain dialogues and songs in the play incited violence in villages, leading to law-and-order problems (Rajulapudi). This news report highlights the delicate balance between artistic freedom and social standards.

The Minister of Endowments, Vellampalli Srinivasa Rao, informed the media that Arya Vaishya community objections prompted the government's ban on the play, citing perceived community disparagement (Rao). His speech emphasized the delicate essence of communal identity.

The rebel to the ruling party, Raghu Ramakrishna Raju, who serves as the Member of Parliament for Narasapuram, lodged a Public Interest Litigation (PIL) in the high court challenging the prohibition of Chinthamani. From his point of view, the government's decision is intended to impress the community in order to gain political benefit for the ruling party. The main point of his PIL was to underscore the importance of artistic freedom and the contribution of art in addressing social issues. He questioned the government's decision, points out that the play has 11 characters from diverse backgrounds, but the ban was based solely on one character's objection, disregarding the representation of others ("MP Moves HC").

The Andhra Pradesh High Court asked MP Raghurama Krishnam Raju about his interest in the Chinthamani PIL ("What Is Your Interest"). In reply, Raju mentioned a Supreme Court judgment that addressed

limiting artistic freedom. The court then highlighted that one group's livelihood should not negatively impact another group's sentiments. It stressed the need for judicial review in such situations. It also pointed out that both groups have the right to react to each other's actions. Then, the court adjourned the hearing to February 23, 2022. In this case, the contradiction between artistic freedom and political influence is clearly evident. It emphasized the judiciary's role in resolving cultural and political tensions in this instance.

6. Conclusion:

The performances of Chinthamani have profoundly affected numerous individuals and caused significant controversy in Telugu theatre history. The play was originally intended to address social issues like prostitution through a story of moral and spiritual transformation. The intention of the play relevant at all times. However, over the course of time, different theatre groups have added obscene scenes to the original play. The adaptations, which were intended for modern spectators, fundamentally changed the intent of the original play and initiated a dialogue concerning cultural preservation and artistic integrity. Eventually, the proliferation of these provocative adaptations prompted government action, which culminated in the official prohibition of the play.

Based on the perspective of the Telugu theatre community, this study addressed the delicate balance between artistic freedom and societal sensitivities, as well as censorship and cultural regulation in the arts. The research highlights the effects of the ban on theatre community, and how they faced financial and professional obstacles as a result of the prohibition. The findings show that the theatre community heavily leans on social media to mobilize support and advocate for their protest against the ban. The theatre community utilizes these digital platforms to effectively engage in broad communication.

Additionally, theatre community suggests solutions to maintain a balance between artistic expression and social standards, including the removal of explicit content, the establishment of review committees, adherence to the original script, and participation in legal and formal protests. The recommended solutions showcase a deep comprehension

of the problem and a readiness to participate in positive conversations with government officials. They address to preserve the integrity and cultural significance of the play.

Overall, this research advocates for a balanced approach to censorship that considers both artistic freedom and social standards. In light of the dynamic nature of theatre, the research highlights the need for a regulatory framework to protect cultural heritage and promote artistic development. The theatre community emphasizes the need for dialogue and cooperation between them and the government. Their responses reveal that theatre remains a vital medium for social commentary. The collaborative approach of theatre practitioners probably serves as model for addressing similar conflicts in other artistic domains. The study provides an understanding of contemporary Telugu theatre by looking at debates surrounding Chinthamani. Furthermore, the study opens up avenues for further research into the relationship between performing arts and modern social expectations. The future research may also explore the role of gender in the evolution of various interpretations in current generation. For future research, the researchers may depend on feminist theory. This theory may offer new dimensions into gender dynamics, character motivation, and cultural inferences.

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